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IN SEARCH OF A LOST BYZANTINE MONUMENT:
SAINT SOPHIA OF NICOSIA

The Gothic cathedral of Saint Sophia in Nicosia was built in the 13th century by the Latin archbishops of Cyprus after the establishment of the Lusignan régime on the island. It is assumed that its dedication to the Holy Wisdom, rather unusual for a Latin shrine, was inherited from an earlier Greek church, presumably the city's cathedral in Byzantine times. Indeed, many a provincial Byzantine city in both Late Antiquity and the medieval period adopted this dedication for their main shrine, following of course the example of Constantinople: the cathedrals of Edessa, Nicaea and Thessalonike, as well as those of cities in the cultural orbit of Byzantium such as Ohrid, Kiev and Benevento, were all dedicated to the Holy Wisdom.¹ But Nicosia's Saint Sophia is not mentioned in any narrative source of the Byzantine period, nor has it been identified with any surviving or excavated building in the city. It must have stood on or in the vicinity of the site where the Gothic structure stands today, in the centre of the walled city.

There is, nevertheless, one small but enormously valuable relevant piece of written evidence. A note written in an 11th-century manuscript of homilies by Saint John Chrysostom (Par.gr. 625, f. 282v.) attests to the existence in Nicosia during the Comnenian period of not only a mere shrine, but almost certainly an episcopal church dedicated to Saint Sophia. Since this is the sole testimony pertaining to the city's Byzantine cathedral, it is worth giving the full Greek text here:²

1. *The Oxford Dictionary of Byzantium* vol. 1, pp. 281, 676; vol.2, pp. 895, 1128, 1464; vol. 3, p. 1514.

2. Published in V.Laurent, 'Les monnaies tricéphales de Jean Comnène. Notes de numismatique byzantine et d'histoire chypriote', *Revue Numismatique* 5 (1951), pp. 97-107 and C. Chatzipsaltes, 'Σημειώσεις αναφερόμεναι εις την ιστορίαν της βυζαντινής Κύπρου', in *Καθηγήτρια. Essays presented to Joan Hussey*, ed. J. Chrysostomides, Camberley 1988, pp. 345-351.

Ἦγοράσθη ἡ βίβλος αὐτή, ἦγουν ἡ ἑξαήμερος / παρὰ τοῦ ἀγιωτάτου καθηγουμένου τῆς μο(νῆς) / Κίκου (μον)αχ(οῦ) κυρ(οῦ) Δα(υίδ) ἀπό τοῦ (μον)αχ(οῦ) Λουκᾶ τοῦ / καθεζομένου εἰς τὴν ἀρχιεπισκο(πὴν) τοῦ Ἀβλέπου / κατενόπ(ιον) τοῦ εὐλαβε(τά)τ(ου) ἱερέως Παναγιώτη κ(αί) καλιγρά(φου) / κ(αί) προσμοναρίου τῆς ἁγίας Σοφίας κ(υ)ροῦ Λέοντος τοῦ αἰγ(εο) / πελαγίτου ὃ καὶ ταύτην τὴν βίβλον προξενήσας / πρό(ς) τὸν προσηθέντ(α) καθηγουμένον / ἡς νομίσματα τρικέφ(αλ)α τῆς προτιμομέ(νης) χαρα(γῆς) τοῦ κρατ(αίου) ἡμῶν βα(σι)λ(έως) / ἦτοι ἁγιογεωργάτ(α) ὀκτώ ἐπὶ βασιλείας κ(υρ)οῦ Ἰω(άννου) κ(αί) πορ / φυρογεννήτου τοῦ κομηννοῦ κ(αί) δουκὸς Κύπρου Κωνσταν / τίνου τῆς ζ(η)μῆδ'

According to this note, in 1135/36 the hegumen of Kykko David bought the manuscript from the monk of the archbishopric Luke Ablepes before two witnesses: the priest Panagiotes and the calligrapher and *prosmonarios* (custodian) of Saint Sophia Leo Aigaiopelagites. Although the place where the transaction took place is not mentioned, the references to Kykko and to the *doux* of Cyprus leave no doubt that this was on the island and almost certainly in its administrative capital Nicosia, since no other church of Saint Sophia is attested on Cyprus in the medieval period. More importantly, this is also indicated by the mention of the archbishopric. In fact, this text provides the earliest dated attestation of the presence of the archbishops in Nicosia, showing that by the early 12th century, and probably considerably earlier, the seat of the Church of Cyprus had been transferred from Salamis / Constantia following its demise in the early medieval period and the reintegration of Cyprus within the empire in 965.³ Saint Sophia must have surely served as the church of the metropolitans of Cyprus.

The process through which the surviving 13th-century building replaced the earlier structure remains undocumented. It is very unlikely that the leadership of the newly established Latin Church would have ordered the demolition of the Orthodox shrine. The history of the Crusaders in the East provides no such precedent: churches were usually taken over and, if necessary, rebuilt or added to, like the Holy Sepulchre of Jerusalem or Saint George of Lydda; those that had fallen earlier in Muslim hands, like the churches of Antioch, were 're-

3. I shall be discussing these issues in a forthcoming article on Nicosia during the Byzantine period, to be published in a volume on the city's history edited by D. Michaelides.

christianized'.⁴ The construction of the Gothic Saint Sophia is thought to have started in ca.1209, although some elements in its north transept doorway (capitals, frieze: fig.1) point towards a slightly earlier date for parts of the building, perhaps during the brief Templar domination (June 1191-April 1192) that followed Richard the Lionheart's conquest.⁵ Assuming that the Byzantine church stood at exactly the same spot, then its disappearance should be placed in the last decade of the 12th century or in the very first years of the 13th, perhaps during one of the earthquakes that shook Cyprus in 1202 and 1203/4,⁶ or as a result of some other, unrecorded calamity.

There is, however, an alternative and, it has to be stressed at the outset, highly speculative answer to this problem, involving the site of the ruinous late Gothic church known as the Bedesten (from its use as a market in Ottoman times)⁷ right next to the Latin cathedral (fig.2). The Bedesten structures stand on top of a late antique basilica parts of which survived into the medieval period. This is indicated, according to M.D. Willis, by the fact that the late Gothic church preserved the floor level of the earlier building (partly excavated in 1935), which was ca.1m50 below the ground level of the surrounding area by the 13th century, as shown by Saint Sophia's floor next door (fig.3); it is also suggested by the use of the 5th-century main apse wall to support the centering for the rib vaults of the late Gothic church.⁸

4. Although the Crusaders replaced the porticoed courtyard and chapels to the east of the Anastasis rotunda at the Holy Sepulchre with a new structure in the 12th c. (transept, choir and ambulatory), the shrine's focus, the rotunda rebuilt with imperial Byzantine patronage in the previous century, was maintained [on churches in the kingdom of Jerusalem see D. Pringle, *The Churches of the Crusader Kingdom of Jerusalem. A Corpus*, 2 vols. Cambridge 1993-98; on those at Constantinople taken over after 1204, R. Janin, 'Les sanctuaires de Byzance sous la domination latine (1204-1261)', *Revue des Études Byzantines* 2 (1944), pp. 134-184 and E. Dalleggio d'Alessio, 'Les sanctuaires urbains et suburbains de Byzance sous la domination Latine (1204-1261)', *Revue des Études Byzantines* 11 (1953) p. 50-61].

5. History of the building with bibliography in *The Cartulary of the Cathedral of Holy Wisdom in Nicosia*, ed. N. Coureas and C. Schabel, Nicosia 1997, pp. 48-54.

6. Sources and bibliography in G. Grivaud, *Villages désertés à Chypre (fin XIIe-fin XIXe siècle)*, Nicosia 1998, p. 431.

7. First reported by Cornelis van Bruyn in the late 17th c. [C.D.Cobham, *Excerpta Cypria*, Cambridge 1908, p. 239]; according to the *Threnos of Cyprus* in the aftermath of the Ottoman conquest the church was turned into a mosque [Th. Papadopoulos, *Ο θρήνος της Κύπρου. Κυπριακαὶ Σπουδαί* 44 (1980), p. 35]; as we shall see shortly, in late Lusignan and Venetian times the building served as the Orthodox cathedral of Nicosia.

8. M.D. Willis, 'The Byzantine beginnings of the Bedesten', *Κυπριακαὶ Σπουδαί* 50 (1986), p. 187.

Considering that this early Byzantine basilica stood right next to the site where the Gothic Saint Sophia was built in the 13th century, and in view of the unlikelihood that the Byzantine cathedral was demolished by the Latin clergy, it would be very tempting to suggest that this, and not some other structure beneath the Latin cathedral, was in fact the Byzantine Saint Sophia⁹ which was temporarily taken over by the Latin Church as soon as this was established in 1196, until a new, grander cathedral could be built.¹⁰ When this was sufficiently advanced the Latin clergy moved across the road taking with them the dedication to the Holy Wisdom as well (late 1220s?).

The above suggestion of course is not only speculative but raises as many questions as those it purports to answer. If the old Orthodox cathedral was still standing after the construction of the Gothic Saint Sophia, what was its subsequent fate? Despite the banishment of the Orthodox prelates from the main urban centres after the reduction of the number of their sees from fourteen to four (the decision was taken in 1222 but was only gradually implemented), the Orthodox archbishop was granted in 1260 a church in Nicosia dedicated to Saint Barnabas.¹¹ Although this church is mentioned on several occasions,¹² the sources fail to provide any information on its location

9. The archimandrite Kyprianos reported in the late 18th c. that the Latins took over from the Greeks St Sophia which had been built by Justinian [Archimandrite Kyprianos *Ιστορία χρονολογική της νήσου Κύπρου*, Venice 1788, pp. 104, 395]; the latter part of his statement was almost certainly inspired by the emperor's association with Constantinople's cathedral church.

10. A reference in a papal letter of December 1196 concerning the properties of Nicosia's Latin cathedral (also repeated in a later document of 1202) implies that the Latin clergy took over an already existing church building [Coureas and Schabel, *Cartulary, op. cit.*, pp. 86, 90: 'Locum ipsum in quo prefata Nicosiensis ecclesia sita est'].

11. 'ecclesiam Gregorum beati Barnabe Nicosiensis' [*Ibid.*, p. 201].

12. A canon of St Barnabas is mentioned in 1292 [*Ibid.*, p. 152]; one of the candidates in the disputed election for the vacant Orthodox see of Solea was Theodore, dean of the same church according to a papal document of 1301 [*Acta Romanorum Pontificum ab Innocentio V ad Benedictum X (1276-1304)*, ed. F.M. Delorme and A.L. Tautou, CICO, V, ii, Rome 1954, pp. 219-23; English translation in C. Schabel, *The Synodicon Nicosiense and other Documents of the Latin Church of Cyprus, 1196-1373*, Nicosia 2001, pp. 333-39 with commentary on pp. 74-75; see also N. Coureas, *The Latin Church in Cyprus, 1195-1312*, Aldershot 1997, pp. 313-14]; in 1305/6 a divorce decision was read in St Barnabas 'at the archbishopric' [S. Lampros, 'Κυπριακά και άλλα έγγραφα εκ του Παλατινού κώδικος 367 της βιβλιοθήκης του Βατικανού', *Νέος Ελληνομνημιών*, 15 (1921), p. 158; although there is no doubt about the year given -(6)814 indiction 4- the precise date remains uncertain; *Dated Greek Manuscripts from Cyprus to the Year 1570*, ed. C.N. Constantinides and R.

which may have been at some distance from the old Byzantine and the new Gothic cathedrals.¹³ Jean Darrouzès has plausibly suggested that Saint Barnabas may have served as the Orthodox archbishop's base in Nicosia since the period following the meeting of Famagusta (1222).¹⁴ We may go even further, however, and suggest, albeit with much caution, that Saint Barnabas was perhaps the Orthodox archbishops' church as early as the take-over of the Byzantine Saint Sophia by the Latin clergy in the 1190s.

The fate of the old Orthodox cathedral in the period immediately following the move of the Latin clergy to the new Saint Sophia is not known. There is no evidence on whether it was returned to Greek hands or not. How it was destroyed and when it was replaced by the late Gothic church remains, once more, a matter of speculation. The chronology of the various building phases at the Bedesten is utterly confusing. The present twin south aisle appears to belong to the earliest among the surviving Gothic structures (14th century?) and was apparently added while the nave of the Byzantine church was still standing (fig.4); it may reflect the layout of the late antique structure, with a south aisle and an additional aisle attached to it.¹⁵ It was later replaced by the domed nave and north aisle surviving to this day, perhaps after one of the numerous earthquakes known to have affected Nicosia in late Lusignan and Venetian times (fig.5).¹⁶

Browning, Nicosia 1997, p. 157 give 2 November 1305]; a sanctuary of St Barnabas in Ledra/Nicosia is also mentioned in the context of the martyrdom of the presbyter Aristokles in early Christian times [H. Delehaye, 'Saints de Chypre', *Analecta Bollandiana* 26 (1907), p. 260], although our source, the *synaxarion* of Constantinople, is of course much later.

13. The site of the Bedesten has been suggested as a possible (although rather unlikely) location [P.I. Kirmitses, 'Ιστορικά ειδήσεις περί καθέδρας και καθεδρικού ναού του ορθοδόξου αρχιεπισκόπου Κύπρου', *Κυπριακά Σπουδαί* 4 (1940), pp. 101-102; see also G. Hill, *A History of Cyprus*, 4 vols. Cambridge 1940-1952, vol. 3, p. 1129 note 1]; Dikigoropoulos mistakenly identified it with St Barnabas of Salamis, concluding that the archbishops of Cyprus still resided at their old metropolitan seat [A.I. Dikigoropoulos, *Cyprus 'Betwixt Greeks and Saracens'*, AD 647-965, Oxford D. Phil Thesis 1961, p. 102 note 1].

14. J. Darrouzès, 'Textes synodaux chypriotes', *Revue des Études Byzantines* 37 (1979), p. 32.

15. Willis, 'Bedestan', *op. cit.*, pp. 186, 188; the complex chronology of the Gothic structures is discussed by Thierry Soulard in the forthcoming acts of the colloquium entitled *Identités croisées en un milieu méditerranéen: le cas de Chypre* (held at Rouen in March 2004).

16. Possibly after the particularly destructive earthquake of 1491 when the choir vaults of St Sophia collapsed; sources and bibliography for quakes in 1453, 1478, 1481, 1491 and 1497 (?) in Grivaud, *Villages, op. cit.*, pp. 431-32; on 1491 in particular, see T. Stavrides, 'Ο σεισμός του 1491 στην Κύπρο', *Επετηρίδα του Κέντρου Επιστημονικών Ερευνών*, 24 (1998), pp. 124-144.

The Bedesten is often said to have been originally dedicated to Saint Nicholas. This is the best place to discuss briefly this commonly held assumption which is based on very thin evidence indeed. Giovanni Mariti in the 1760s identified a figure holding a book on the upper lintel of the main doorway of the north façade at the Bedesten (fig.6) with Saint Nicholas and was probably the first to propose this dedication for the church, based solely on the evidence of the lintel (fig.7). Subsequent authors, including Camille Enlart, accepted the identification.¹⁷ This led to other suggestions involving various churches dedicated to saint Nicholas and known from later medieval sources to have existed in Nicosia, most notably those belonging to the Augustinian canons (attested in 1237) and to the Order of Saint Thomas (1357), although the sources offer no clues concerning the location of either within the city.¹⁸ Let us look more closely at the one and only piece of evidence: the monolithic lintel with the figure in relief also bears six armorial shields which clearly date from the 16th century,¹⁹ indicating that the entire piece was almost certainly carved and inserted at that time (fig.8). This is significant because even if the figure does indeed represent Nicholas, it would perhaps provide an indication of the shrine's dedication only for this late period;²⁰ but as we shall see next, it is precisely in this very period that we do have secure documentary evidence for the dedication of the Bedesten, known in late Lusignan and Venetian times as the Virgin Hodegetria.

Several late 14th-century marginal notes in the Par.gr.1589 (published by Jean Darrouzès) mention a church dedicated to the Virgin Hodegetria in

17. G. Mariti, *Viaggi per l'isola di Cipro e per la Soria e per la Palestina*, vol. 1, Lucca 1769, p. 99; C. Enlart, *L'art gothique et la renaissance en Chypre*, 2 vols. Paris 1899, vol. 1, pp. 150-51. The archimandrite Kyprianos, writing in Venice in the 1780s, had perhaps in mind Mariti's account, published in Lucca in 1769, when he reported that according to 'common tradition' the Bedesten had been a Greek church dedicated to St Nicholas [Kyprianos, *Ιστορία*, *op. cit.*, p. 395].

18. Enlart, *Gothique*, *op. cit.*, vol. 1, pp. 150-51 [C. Enlart, *Gothic Art and the Renaissance in Cyprus*, transl. by D. Hunt, London 1987, pp. 136-37], Coureas, *Latin Church*, *op. cit.*, pp. 180 note 274, 242 note 285.

19. G. Jeffery, *A Description of the Historic Monuments of Cyprus*, Nicosia 1918, repr. London 1983, pp. 84-87, where the Nicholas dedication is also reluctantly refuted primarily because of chronological considerations.

20. Kirmitses, who suggests that the Bedesten may be the church of St Barnabas mentioned earlier, also proposes a tentative identification of the figure with Barnabas [Kirmitses, 'Ιστορικά ειδήσεις', *op. cit.*, p. 103.

Nicosia, while two later notes (dated to 1516) in the same manuscript and a document of 1454 from Genoa pertaining to the Podocataro family refer to the Chrysodegetria / Hodegetria as the Orthodox cathedral.²¹ The 'Crussotheistrie' which Etienne de Lusignan mentions as Nicosia's Greek cathedral in the 16th century, and the 'petite église de grecq ... en l'honneur de Nostre-Dame' described by Jacques le Saige in 1518 as being next to Saint Sophia, certainly refer to the same building, the Bedesten, which by 1507 was the Greek bishop's church according to Pierre Mésenge.²² It is clear then that at least since the mid-15th century the Bedesten was functioning as Nicosia's Orthodox cathedral, assuming the role of its predecessor on the site after acquiring a new dedication.²³ It is likely that this occurred in the course of the 14th century, a period that witnessed a rise in the fortunes of the Orthodox Church, most eloquently illustrated by the construction of the large new Greek cathedral of Saint George at Famagusta.

A second problem created by the above suggestion concerns the appearance and architectural type of Nicosia's Byzantine cathedral. Of course no description of the long lost Saint Sophia has survived. There is, however, some tantalising evidence. A now lost lead seal belonging to the Latin archbishop of Nicosia Eustorge de Montaigu (1217-50) and bearing a depiction of a building with the inscription 'Ecclesia Nicossiensis' was attached to a document of 1217 in the Archives of the Order of Saint John of the Hospital in

21. J. Darrouzès, 'Notes pour servir à l'histoire de Chypre', *Κυπριακαί Σπουδαί* 17 (1953), pp. 89-92; C. Otten-Froux, 'Les investissements financiers des chypriotes en Italie', in *Κύπρος - Βενετία. Κοινές ιστορικές τύχες*, ed. C. Maltezos, Venice 2002, p. 128.

22. E. Lusignan, *Description de toute l'isle de Cypre*, Paris 1580, f. 31r.; Cobham, *Excerpta*, *op. cit.*, 1908, p. 58; Enlart, *Gothique*, *op. cit.*, vol.2, 715 [Enlart/Hunt, *Gothic*, *op. cit.*, p. 137]; also Jeffery, *Historic Monuments*, *op. cit.*, 1918, p. 84; Le Saige's description of the Bedesten as 'une petite église', despite the substantial size of the building, is not surprising considering that he must have been familiar with the large collegiate church of St Peter's in his home town of Douai (rebuilt in the 18th c.) as well as with cathedrals in northern France; thus, in his view even St Sophia is also a little church. The Theotokos Hodegetria is also attested in the undated colophon of the Vat. gr. 2194 which was copied for this church [J. Darrouzès, 'Notes pour servir à l'histoire de Chypre', *Κυπριακαί Σπουδαί*, 20 (1956), p. 55].

23. Leontios Machairas' unconfirmed report that the Hodegetria used to house the tomb of St Triphyllios [Leontios Makhairas, *Recital concerning the Sweet Land of Cyprus entitled 'Chronicle'*, ed. R.M. Dawkins, 2 vols. Oxford 1932, vol. 1, p. 34] would offer additional evidence concerning the status of this church as Nicosia's cathedral, since Triphyllios was the most prominent occupant of the early Christian see of Ledra.

Malta (fig.9); it is known from a sketch first published in the 18th century.²⁴ This elaborate yet confusing representation has caused a mild controversy. It has been interpreted in turn as a symbolic representation, as an illustration of the earliest phase of the Gothic cathedral, and as a depiction of the Byzantine cathedral.²⁵ It shows a building crowned by a disproportionately large bulbous dome with windows in its high drum. The façade has three gables (?) over a multitude of arched forms which may represent doors, windows or apses. To the left stand two slim and tall towers (or turrets?), perhaps domed too and attached to another tall structure (buttress? tower?).

The first alternative, that of a symbolic representation, is untenable in view of the idiosyncratic depiction of the building. Had this been the case, one would have expected a much simpler sketch, like those representing the city of Nicosia as a fortified city gate on contemporary seals.²⁶ The suggestion that the drawing may represent the Latin cathedral in its early phase also has to be dismissed once and for all. It is based on the assumption that the early Lusignan building was domed. This is allegedly supported by a much later reference: according to the surviving Italian version of his will, Jean Audeth in 1451 bequeathed 50 bezants 'per fabricar la cuba in Santa Sophya'.²⁷ If indeed the meaning of the term *cuba* in this context is that of a dome,²⁸ then the 15th-century document perhaps refers to a smaller structure over one of the annexes, although there is no other evidence that building work was being carried out in the cathedral in this period. What is more, the amount left by the

24. S. Pauli, *Codice diplomatico del sacro ordine militare Gerosolimitano*, Lucca 1733, pl. V no. 48 [plates inserted between pp. 343-46], best reproduced in D.M. Metcalf, 'The Iconography and Style of Crusader Seals in Cyprus', in *Cyprus and the Crusades*, ed. N. Coureas and J. Riley-Smith, Nicosia 1995, pp. 365-375.

25. Different views and bibliography in Coureas and Schabel, *Cartulary*, *op. cit.*, pp. 49-50.

26. Metcalf, 'Iconography', *op. cit.*, p. 367.

27. J. Richard, 'Une famille des Vénitiens blancs dans le royaume de Chypre au milieu du XVe siècle: Les Audeth et la seigneurie du Marethasse', *Rivista di studi bizantini e slavi*, 1 [Miscellanea Agostino Pertusi, I] Bologna 1981, p. 113 and note 6 (repr. in *Croisés, missionnaires et voyageurs: les perspectives orientales du monde Latin médiéval*, London, 1983); the assumption is that this dome was subsequently replaced by a rib vault.

28. This is of course the usual meaning of the word [*Grande dizionario della lingua italiana*], although it can also mean an underground chamber or cistern [*Lexicon latinitatis medii aevi*] and sometimes even a fountain or well enclosed within a domed structure [*Vocabolario della lingua italiana*].

testator is only a tiny fraction of what he bequeathed to the Jacobite church of Nicosia for his sepulchre and of the sum he left to be distributed on the day of his burial (50 compared to 400 and 1000 bezants respectively). More importantly, although according to the domed scheme theory the dome shown on the seal must have been in existence in the early 13th century, Audeth's will implies that the *cuba* was under construction in 1451 - unless of course it refers to a campaign of repairs, something that cannot be ascertained. An additional indication against the dome hypothesis is provided by the (usually brief) descriptions of the church by medieval visitors which do not contain any allusion to a dome: Martoni in 1394 only mentions the painted vaults of the cathedral.²⁹

It is, however, the building itself that offers the most valuable clues. The most likely position for a dome would obviously be over the transept crossing (fig.10).³⁰ Yet not only is the crossing bay rectangular, precluding the construction of a circular dome base,³¹ but the structure itself would have offered little lateral buttressing for a dome, and a relatively large one at that (diameter: ca.10m): the transept vaults are much lower, at the same level as those of the aisles from which they are indistinguishable; the flying buttresses on top of them, at the four corners of the crossing bay, although the oldest preserved in the cathedral, were clearly added as an afterthought and could not have withstood the pressure exerted by such a large dome (fig.11).³² And there

29. 'facta ad lamiam, et tota ipsa lamia ab archoro versus altare magnum est picta cum azolo fino et stellis aureis' [L. Legrand, 'Relation du pèlerinage à Jérusalem de Nicolas de Martoni, notaire italien (1394-1395)', *Revue de l'Orient Latin* 3 (1895), p. 635; English translation in Cobham, *Excerpta*, *op. cit.*, 1908, p. 26]; for the use of the term *lamia/lamina* in an architectural context in medieval sources, see the *Novum glossarium mediae latinitatis*, *The British Academy Dictionary of Medieval Latin from British Sources*, ed. R.E. Latham, Oxford 1965, 1983 and in particular, the *Grande dizionario della lingua italiana* (for its use by Boccaccio in the 14th c.).

30. By the beginning of Eustorge's tenure the nave had not been built yet [Enlart, *Gothique*, *op. cit.*, vol. 1, pp. 81 and 140-41; Enlart/Hunt, *Gothic*, *op. cit.*, p. 83]; the variation in the length of its bays clearly reflects its piecemeal construction.

31. In Byzantine architecture, and in particular on Cyprus, irregular domes on anything but a square plan occur frequently; they would be totally out of tune, however, with the character of Gothic architecture on the island, whose construction method contrasts sharply with that of the vast majority of surviving (mostly rural) monuments from the Byzantine period.

32. The crossing buttresses do not bond with the wall masonry [Enlart, *Gothique*, *op. cit.*, vol. 1, pp. 8 and 108-10; Enlart/Hunt, *Gothic*, *op. cit.*, pp. 37 and 100].

is no doubt that, despite the earthquake damage suffered by the building in subsequent centuries, the often extensive repairs necessitated did not result in the alteration of its layout:³³ that is to say, the length of its bays remained unchanged - there never was a bay structurally suitable to receive a dome.

Examples of churches with a dome over the crossing are well known in the 12th-century Crusader architecture of the Holy Land (cathedral of Tyre, Saint Anne in Jerusalem, possibly Saint George of Lydda and the cathedral of Nazareth). Unlike Saint Sophia, however, these were built with a high transept which allowed the adequate transfer of the dome charges.³⁴ The early Gothic architecture of Cyprus, on the other hand, provides no analogy for the use of rib vaulting in combination with a dome. The small church at the abbey of Bellapais, one of the admittedly few surviving contemporary buildings, would be a perfect candidate for such a scheme: it has a high transept whose vaults together with those of the nave and sanctuary, could have easily supported the charges of a dome (diameter: ca.7m) over the square crossing;³⁵ yet this was covered with a rib vault.

So, if the seal shows neither a symbolic representation nor the earliest phase of the Gothic church, the inevitable conclusion is that it is the Byzantine cathedral which is depicted. What information on its architecture can be extracted from this depiction then? Although it is unclear which façade is

33. The most severe damage appears to have occurred in 1491 when the choir vault collapsed [Stavrídes, 'Ο σεισμός', *op. cit.*, 1998, pp. 130-33]; the rebuilding may have affected the lowest parts of the structure too, and in particular the choir columns [Enlart *Gothique, op. cit.*, vol. 1, p. 96; Enlart/Hunt, *Gothic, op. cit.*, p. 94] which Jeffery in fact suggests were erected during the subsequent repairs [G. Jeffery, *The Mosques of Nicosia* Cyprus Monuments. Historical and architectural buildings no. 7, Nicosia 1935, p. 14].

34. T.S.R. Boase, 'Ecclesiastical Art in the Crusader States in Palestine and Syria', in *A History of the Crusades*, general editor K.M. Setton, 6 vols. Philadelphia/Madison 1955-1989, vol. 4, ed. H.W. Hazard (1977), pp. 93-94, 106; J. Folda, *The Art of the Crusaders in the Holy Land, 1098-1197*, Cambridge 1995, pp. 133-36; D. Pringle, *The Churches, op. cit.* vol. 2, pp. 9-27 and 125; the same applies to the 14th-c. Santi Giovanni e Paolo (Zanipolo) in Venice which had a dome added over its high transept crossing in the 15th c. [on this building's chronology see D. Howard, *The Architectural History of Venice*, New Haven/London 2002, pp. 76-77].

35. Enlart, *Gothique, op. cit.*, vol. 1, pp. 203-11 [Enlart/Hunt, *Gothic, op. cit.*, pp. 179-87], and B.Kitsiki-Panagopoulos, *Cistercian and Mendicant Monasteries in Medieval Greece*. Chicago/London 1979, p. 115, for the possibility that the transept vaulting may have been altered.

shown, its division in three bays may possibly reflect the layout of a domed cross-in-square structure. Indeed, it has even been suggested that the four column shafts and two of the capitals in the choir of the Gothic Saint Sophia may be the remnants of such a building (fig.12).³⁶ Such a hypothesis, however, would presuppose the destruction of the early building before the construction of the new cathedral. These elements could in fact have come from any earlier site within or outside Nicosia.

Now, if we accept that the predecessor of the Bedesten was the Byzantine cathedral, how can the archaeological evidence be reconciled with that from the seal sketch? The former is confined to the eastern part of the building: only the main apse and part of the northern apse were exposed in 1935 when the site was investigated, in addition to some walls belonging to annex buildings (fig.13). The late antique church was obviously a timber-roofed basilica, quite different from the domed church shown on the seal. It is very unlikely that this early basilica would have survived intact into the 13th century; there is little evidence to suggest that any of the numerous late antique churches of Cyprus were still standing at that time.³⁷ Indeed, it is well known that many were altered, rebuilt, or replaced by domed schemes in the medieval period.³⁸ What is more, if these medieval buildings incorporated any part of their predecessors to their structure, this was very often the apse. It is precisely this very process which may have occurred on the site of the Bedesten too, whose late antique apse, as we have already seen, was still standing in medieval times. A rebuilding of the early basilica as a domed

36. A. Papageorgiou, 'Crusader Influence on the Byzantine Art of Cyprus', in *Cyprus and the Crusades*, ed. N. Coureas and J. Riley-Smith, Nicosia 1995, p. 276; further comments and bibliography in T. Papacostas, *Byzantine Cyprus: The Testimony of its Churches, 650-1200*, Oxford D. Phil Thesis, 1999, vol. 1, p. 148 and vol. 2, pp. 133-34; choir columns shown in Enlart, *op. cit.*, vol. 1, p. 97 fig.34.

37. On the effects of earthquakes on the development of ecclesiastical architecture in Byzantine Cyprus and their role in the loss of early Christian monuments see S. Ćurčić, 'Byzantine architecture on Cyprus: An introduction to the problem of the genesis of a regional style', in *Medieval Cyprus, Studies in Art, Architecture and History in Memory of Doula Mouriki*, eds. N. Patterson Ševčenko and C. Moss, Princeton 1999, pp. 71-91.

38. E.g. the Panagia Kanakaria and St Prokopios at Syngrasis, among many examples A.H.S. Megaw and E.J.W. Hawkins, *The Church of Panagia Kanakaria at Lythrankomi in Cyprus. Its Mosaics and Frescoes*, Dumbarton Oaks Studies 14, Washington D.C., 1977, pp. 34-36; T. Papacostas, 'A tenth-century inscription from Syngrasis, Cyprus', *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies*, 26 (2002), pp. 46-47; other cases include St Barnabas at Salamis/Constantia, the Angeloktisti at Kiti, and St Tychikos near Ayia Phyla (Limassol).

church would be in accordance with both the prevalent pattern in other monuments on the island and Nicosia's rise in the middle Byzantine period.

One last point that merits some attention is the tall structure shown to the left of the church on Eustorge's seal. Assuming again that this is a fairly accurate representation of the Byzantine cathedral, at least in its main elements (dome, tower, three-bay façade), the most likely function for the tower would be that of a belfry. Unfortunately, no comparative contemporary material survives on the ground. The Orthodox ecclesiastical architecture of Cyprus has not preserved any bell-towers from before the late Ottoman period.³⁹ Moreover, there is no source evidence for the use of bells or the existence of church towers on Byzantine Cyprus: the surviving *typika* of three monasteries founded during the Comnenian period, namely Koutsovendis, the Enkleistra and Machairas,⁴⁰ only refer to the use of a wooden or metal *semantron* to summon the monks to the church or the refectory and do not contain any mention of a specific structure associated with this. The island's Latin churches of the Lusignan era, on the other hand, were provided with both belfries and bells.⁴¹ A royal decree of 1373 forbade the sounding of bells and

39. The set of drawings made by Edmond Duthoit in the 1860s is a precious source: it shows that by this date the belfries at the churches of Lefkara and Tochni had already been erected, while those at Rizokarpaso and Peristerona had not been built yet [R. Severis and L. Bonato, *Along the Most Beautiful Path in the World. Edmond Duthoit and Cyprus* (Nicosia 1999), pp. 171-77]; note also that Barskyj's drawings (1730s) do not contain any evidence for bell-towers in Greek churches; the Russian monk reports that bells were banned after 1571, and that in towns even the *semantron* was forbidden [A.D. Grishin, *A Pilgrim's Account of Cyprus: Bar'skyj's Travels in Cyprus*, Sources for the History of Cyprus 3, New York 1996, pp. 17, 51 and pl. 1-18].

40. That of Koutsovendis is a liturgical *typikon*; its unpublished sections contain several references to various types of *semantra* used in the monastery [A.A. Dmitrievski, *Opisanie liturgiĉeskikh rukopisej*, vol. 3, Saint Petersburg 1917, p. 124; Par. gr. 402, ff. 42v, 112v, 125r, 134v, 237v, 238v]; the *typika* of the Enkleistra and Machairas are foundation charters [J.P. Tsiknopoullos, *Κυπριακά Τυπικά*, Nicosia 1969, pp. 20, 23, 24, 49, 94, 109].

41. The texts pertaining to the Latin Church of Cyprus published by C. Schabel contain numerous references to bells [Schabel, *Synodicum*, *op. cit.*, pp. 90, 104, 168, 204, 297 for the 13th c.; see also Coureas and Schabel, *Cartulary*, *op. cit.*, p. 176]; the accounts of the Latin bishopric of Limassol in 1367 also contain a reference to bells, while a document of 1466 concerning Notre-Dame la Miséricordieuse in Nicosia mentions its 'canpanerie' with three bells [J. Richard, *Chypre sous les Lusignans. Documents chypriotes des archives du Vatican (XIVe et XVe siècles)*, Paris 1962, p. 97 and *idem*, *Le livre des remembrances de la secrète du royaume de Chypre (1468-1469)*, Nicosia 1983, pp. 94 and 185 note 11]; in the 14th c. both St Nicholas of Famagusta and St Sophia of Nicosia were provided with towers on their western façades, while the latter is also reported to have acquired bells in the same period ['Chronique d'Amadi', in *Chroniques d'Amadi et de Strambaldi*, ed. R. de Mas Latrie,

semantra at night in Nicosia in anticipation of an imminent Genoese attack, showing that at least by this time both were in use.⁴² According to Felix Faber (1483) the Greek churches of Nicosia had 'towers and wooden instruments with which they summon the people to divine service', although their Latin counterparts used bells.⁴³ Travellers of the Venetian and Ottoman periods confirm this, for they remark that in the island's Orthodox churches and monasteries only the *semantron* was employed, although they speak of towers too, implying that perhaps this may have hung from them.⁴⁴

A 15th-century drawing offers some intriguing albeit inconclusive evidence: accompanying the account of Conrad von Grünemberg who visited Cyprus in 1486, it shows 'Sallina' (Larnaca) and, near the shore, a three-aisled multi-domed church with three apses which is certainly the basilica of Saint Lazaros, built in the middle Byzantine period (11th century?).⁴⁵ A tall ruinous

vols. Paris 1891-1893, vol. I, p. 406]; San Salvatore, the formerly Greek church used by the Ethiopian/Abyssinian community of Nicosia in the 15th and 16th c., is also reported to have had bells [R. Lefevre, 'Roma e la comunità etiopica di Cipro nei secoli XV e XVI', *Rassegna di Studi Etiopici* 1/1, Rome 1941, p. 77]. Enlart excavated the remains of bells in a church in Famagusta [C. Enlart, 'Fouilles dans les églises de Famagouste de Chypre', *Archaeological Journal* 62 (1905), p. 196].

42. Reported by Leontios Machairas [Machairas, *Recital*, *op. cit.*, vol. 1, p. 362, §383.]

43. Cobham, *Excerpta*, *op. cit.*, p. 42.

44. As in the Great Lavra on Mount Athos in the 11th c. [G. Millet, 'Recherches au Mont-Athos', *Bulletin de Correspondence Hellénique* 29 (1905), p. 126]; there is no evidence that the Bedesten, at least as it survives today, ever had a belfry [Enlart, *Gothique*, *op. cit.*, vol. 1, p. 153; Enlart/Hunt, *Gothic*, *op. cit.*, p. 139]; Jacques le Saige (1518) marvelled at the loud sound produced by a *semantron* in Nicosia, while Girolamo Dandini (1596) lamented the ruined belfries of the city's churches after the Ottoman conquest [Cobham, *Excerpta*, *op. cit.*, pp. 59, 161]; an icon of the Virgin Hodegetria (dated to 1529) from the church of St Kassianos in Nicosia shows the donor couple in front of a basilica to which an exceptionally tall Italianate belfry is attached [Papageorgiou, *Icons of Cyprus*, Nicosia 1992, pl. 88]; earlier and perhaps more realistic representations of church models with donor portraits in fresco cycles from small rural churches, however (Galata, Moutoulas, Pedoulas, Dali), do not show belfries [A. and J. Stylianou, *The Painted Churches of Cyprus*, London 1985, pp. 91, 324, 332, 427].

45. Drawing published in G. Rossi-Osmida, 'Il regno di Cipro e Venezia', in *Documenti inediti di Cipro antica*, ed. V. Karageorghis, Centro Studi Ricerche Ligabue, Abstackta Archaeologica, Treviso 1998, p. 42, and Grünemberg's account in *Excerpta Cypria Nova. Voyageurs occidentaux à Chypre au XVe siècle*, ed. G. Grivaud, Nicosia 1990, pp. 124-27. On St Lazaros see A. Papageorgiou, 'Ο ναός του Αγίου Λαζάρου στη Λάρνακα', *Report of the Department of Antiquities, Cyprus*, Nicosia 1998, 205-224.

(circular?) tower surmounts or is perhaps attached to its western part. No such structure is known to have existed or survives today at Saint Lazaros (the present-day campanile at the south-east corner dates from the mid-19th century). Even though the drawing cannot be trusted as far as the architectural detail is concerned (as shown by the depiction of Saint Nicholas and the fortifications of Famagusta in the same manuscript), there is no doubt that it remains reliable when it comes to the general layout of the building, as Grünemberg's views of Venice and Jerusalem with their landmark monuments suggest.⁴⁶ The existence of a tower at Saint Lazaros in the 15th century is therefore not in doubt. What remains uncertain is its form, function and date: Is this a belfry, and more importantly, could it be a Byzantine structure? The answer to the first question may be positive; there is however no indication whatsoever about the second which may only be provided by archaeology. If the (bell?) tower at Saint Lazaros could be shown to be of Byzantine date then that of Saint Sophia would not be so exceptional after all in the context of Byzantine architecture on Cyprus.

Until recently it was thought that belfries were introduced to Byzantine church architecture only as a result of western influence, after the Latin conquest of Constantinople in 1204. Although no securely dated examples survive from the middle Byzantine period, their proliferation in Palaeologan times (mostly at Constantinople and in Serbia), and evidence from written sources and illuminated manuscripts suggests that they were not unknown in earlier centuries.⁴⁷ Our depiction of Nicosia's middle Byzantine cathedral may offer an additional piece of evidence in support of the indigenous origin of Byzantine church towers, regardless of whether these were used to hang a bell or a *semantron*. The two domed turrets shown on the seal may represent a

46. Published in A.C.J. Vrankrijker, *De pelgrimstocht Van Ridder Gruenberg naar het Heilige Land in 1486*, Amsterdam 1947, pp. 16, 59.

47. Discussion by S. Ćurčić in E. Kitzinger, *The Mosaics of St Mary's of the Admirals in Palermo*, Washington D.C. 1990, pp. 65-66 and by the same author in 'Bell tower', *The Oxford Dictionary of Byzantium* vol. 1, pp. 279-80, with bibliography. A domed church with a tall elaborate campanile represented in relief on an 11th-c. (?) capital from the no longer surviving church of Saint-Sauveur at Nevers (Burgundy) has been considered since the mid-19th c. as a Byzantine structure [E.E. Viollet-Leduc and L. Gaucherel, 'Eglise byzantine sur un chapiteau Roman', *Annales Archéologiques* 2 (1858), pp. 105-107], but this can hardly be considered as evidence for belfries in Byzantium at that time, since the sculptor's source of inspiration is unlikely to be ever identified and the church is in fact more reminiscent of domed buildings in south-western France than of middle Byzantine structures.

scheme comparable to that adopted for the elaborate campanile of the Martorana at Palermo (finished by 1184), which was originally crowned by one central and perhaps four smaller domes over the corners.⁴⁸

The sequence of events postulated above with regard to Saint Sophia, although purely conjectural, is satisfactory in many respects. It exonerates the Latin Church from an unprecedented act of aggression against its Orthodox counterpart on the island; it is hard to believe that the wanton destruction of the latter's principal shrine, had it occurred, would go unnoticed in contemporary and later Greek sources. It allows for the 'Templar workshop' elements built into the north doorway of the Gothic Saint Sophia to be ascribed to a church begun earlier on the same site but left unfinished, something that would have been impossible had the Byzantine cathedral stood on exactly the same spot. It disposes of the difficulty created by the supposed existence of the cathedral in Byzantine times only a few metres away from a large, still functioning earlier church, on the site of the Bedesten. It also goes a long way in explaining the choice of the latter site to house the new building of the Orthodox cathedral later on. Its main weakness lies of course in that it lacks the necessary corroborating material, an obviously severe shortcoming that only further archaeological investigation at the sites of both the Gothic Saint Sophia and the Bedesten may rectify.

48. The Palermitan campanile has been ascribed to a workshop of masons and sculptors from the Eastern Mediterranean (possibly from Jerusalem) and its basic conception has been identified as Byzantine; discussion and reconstruction by S. Ćurčić in Kitzinger, *The mosaics, op. cit.*, pp. 52-62.

fig. 1 Saint Sophia, Nicosia: detail of the north transept doorway
(photograph by author)

fig. 2 Nicosia: map showing Saint Sophia next to the Bedesten (marked as Saint Nikolaos)
[Department of Lands and Surveys, Nicosia]

*fig. 3 Bedesten, Nicosia: the main apse during the excavation of 1935
[J.R. Hilton Archive, by permission of King's College London]*

*fig. 4 Bedesten, Nicosia: view of the south aisles and nave from the south-west
(photograph by author)*

fig. 6 Bedesten, Nicosia: the north façade
(photograph by author)

fig. 7 Bedesten, Nicosia: detail of the lintel of the main doorway on the north façade (photograph by author)

fig. 8 Bedesten, Nicosia: the tympanum and lintel of the main doorway on the north façade (photograph by author)

fig. 9 Seal of Archbishop Eustorge de Montaigu [Metcalf 1995, fig. 5]

fig. 10 Saint Sophia, Nicosia: plan [Enlart/Hunt 1987, p. 89]

fig. 11 Saint Sophia, Nicosia: flying buttresses over the northern aisle and transept [Enlart/Hunt 1987, p. 106]

fig. 12 Saint Sophia, Nicosia: the four choir columns
(photograph by author)

fig. 13 Bedesten, Nicosia: plan of the excavated remains within the surviving structure / Willis 1986, fig. 11